

A MASS-LOSS MODEL FOR A CARBON-CARBON COMPOSITE
IN A PROTECTIVE GAS ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The overall goal of the theoretical work described in this paper is to establish a practical scheme for protecting a structural carbon-carbon composite from oxidation in high temperature applications involving flows. It is proposed here that the introduction of an inert/synthetic gas into the boundary layer at the carbon composite surface will afford some such protection. A mathematical model has been developed for nonturbulent plug flow in a cylindrical tube made of a carbon-carbon composite material. This model predicts carbon oxidation in the presence or absence of protection provided by the inert nitrogen gas boundary layer flow. Analytical equations are provided to calculate the local oxygen diffusive flux at the tube surface, the local carbon surface mass loss rate, the surface area averaged carbon mass loss rate, and the bulk oxygen concentration. The computed results for typical conditions are presented. The inert gas boundary layer flow reduces the carbon mass loss at the tube surface. We conclude that an inert gas or equilibrium synthetic gas mixture flow in the boundary layer can provide protection to a carbon-carbon composite surface from oxidation.

KEY WORDS: Carbon-Carbon Composite; Carbon Oxidation; Inert/Synthetic Gas; Boundary Layer Protection.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon-carbon composites are structural materials consisting of a carbon matrix reinforced with carbon fibers. Originally used as a thermal protection material for specialized aerospace applications, carbon-carbon composites are now being considered [1] as general purpose, high temperature structural materials.

The high solid dissociation temperature of carbon (sublimes at 3650°C [2]), its outstanding specific strength and stiffness and the retention of mechanical properties at elevated temperatures would seem to make carbon-carbon composites the materials of choice for high temperature structural applications. The operating temperature of current generation gas turbine engines, for example, is limited to less than 1000°C by the stress-rupture properties of the nickel-based superalloys used for its turbine blades and stators [3]. The thermodynamic efficiency of all such heat engines would be dramatically improved by operating at the adiabatic flame temperature of a stoichiometric fuel/air mixture, typically 2200 to 2600K for most hydrocarbons. Furthermore, the nearly four-fold decrease in density (carbon-carbon density is less than 2 g cm^{-3}) could bring enormous weight reductions to rotating engine components and similar benefits to the aerodynamically-heated skins of hypersonic aircraft. If carbon were not susceptible to gasification in the presence of oxidizing agents, all of these applications would seem likely.

To exploit the outstanding elevated temperature mechanical properties of carbon, considerable effort has been devoted to overcoming its oxidation susceptibility via oxygen barrier coatings [4]. Such approaches have met with limited success. However, failure to simultaneously provide a coating material which is oxidation resistant and possesses adhesion, thermal expansion matching and chemical compatibility with the substrate renders such coating systems partially or totally ineffective. Furthermore, mechanical damage to the barrier coating has catastrophic implications for the structural composite operating in a hostile environment. Thus it is improbable that a coating system alone can provide reliable long term protection for a carbon-carbon substrate in a high temperature oxidizing environment. Recently, we proposed [5] the protection of a carbon-carbon material in a hostile environment by exposing it to gas mixtures in equilibrium with structural carbon. By the definition of thermodynamic equilibrium, exposure of carbon surfaces to equilibrium synthetic gas mixtures at the design temperature and pressure conditions should result in negligible carbon loss due to gasification. The compositions of gas mixtures in equilibrium with solid carbon at specific temperatures and pressures were predicted in Phase I of the theoretical development using a computer program NASAODE [6]. We also suggested there that the surface of a structural carbon-carbon material in a practical system could be protected from oxidation by introducing inert/synthetic gas mixtures into the wall surface boundary layer or through pores in the wall of a flowing gas system. In this paper we present a mathematical formulation and computed results depicting how the carbon loss from the wall of a cylindrical carbon tube can be minimized using this approach (Fig. 1). This formulation is designated Phase II of the theoretical development scheme. In this phase, only nitrogen flow in the surface boundary layer is considered to protect the carbon surface from oxygen attack while oxygen diffuses from the inner oxygen-containing stream. Oxygen concentration of 0.5% in the inner stream is typical of that determined by thermodynamic equilibrium calculations for adiabatic, stoichiometric methane/air combustion.

Figure 1. Schematic of test section to be protected from oxidation.

2. PHASE II MODEL EQUATIONS

In Phase II of the theoretical model development scheme to predict carbon loss, a nitrogen stream containing oxygen is considered to flow along the center line as shown in Fig. 1. A protective nitrogen gas stream, initially separated from the inner oxidative stream, is caused to flow along the interior surface of the carbon-carbon tube. The exterior surface of the tube is in an environment of an inert gas such as argon. The model assumptions are given below.

- Fluid is passing through the tube as "plug flow".
- Quasi steady-state and quasi isothermal conditions prevail for the oxygen concentration range (oxygen mole fraction: 0.005 - 0.05) being investigated.
- The oxygen reactive specie diffuses in the radial direction only, i.e., its axial dispersion is neglected relative to its convective transport.
- Oxygen is consumed via heterogeneous chemical reaction at the carbon tube interior surface only.
- Oxygen molecular mass diffusivity in the nonturbulent flow is constant.
- A constant pressure is assumed.

The differential equation describing local oxygen transport by convection along the axial z -coordinate and molecular diffusion along the radial r -coordinate is

$$\langle v_z \rangle \frac{\partial C_{O_2}}{\partial z} = \mathcal{D}_{O_2-m} \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial C_{O_2}}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 C_{O_2}}{\partial r^2} \right] \quad (1) [7]$$

where $\langle v_z \rangle$ is the cross sectional area averaged gas flow velocity; C_{O_2} is the oxygen concentration; and \mathcal{D}_{O_2-m} is the oxygen mass diffusivity.

The model boundary conditions are:

At $z = 0$:

$$C_{O_2} = C_{O_{2,o}} \quad \text{for } 0 < r \leq R_{\text{int},o} \quad (2a)$$

$$= C_{O_{2,o,p}} \quad \text{for } R_{\text{int},o} < r \leq R_t \quad (2b)$$

For any z :

$$\text{at } r=0, \quad \frac{\partial C_{O_2}}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (2c)$$

$$\text{at } r=R_t, \quad \left(-\mathcal{D}_{O_2-m} \frac{\partial C_{O_2}}{\partial r} \right) = k C_{O_2} \quad (2d)$$

(oxygen transport flux at the tube surface) = (oxygen consumption rate by first order reaction with the carbon tube surface via $2C(s) + O_2(g) \rightarrow 2CO(g)$).

Here, $C_{O_{2,o}}$ is the initial oxygen concentration in the inner stream, and $C_{O_{2,o,p}}$ is the initial oxygen concentration in the protective gas boundary layer stream. If the gas boundary layer stream acts as a protective layer, $C_{O_{2,o,p}} = 0$. In the case of no protection provided by this stream, $C_{O_{2,o,p}} = C_{O_{2,o}}$. $R_{\text{int},o}$ is the initial separation distance between the inner oxidative and annular protective stream. R_t is the inner radius of the carbon tube. The first order reaction rate constant, k , for oxygen reaction with carbon to produce carbon monoxide under the low oxygen concentration conditions considered here is given by

$$k = 188.10 \text{ Te}^{-(20130.85/T)}, \frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}} \quad (3) [8]$$

where T is the absolute temperature in K.

The differential model, Eq. (1), and the boundary conditions, Eqs. (2a-2d), were made dimensionless. Solution was then obtained by the method of separation of variables [9] using the mathematical information concerning the Bessel functions [10]. The dimensionless oxygen concentration at any point in the flow field in the tube is given by

$$Y_{O_2} = \sum_{m=1}^{m=\infty} \left[A_m e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_m^2}{\zeta}\right)Z} J_0(\lambda_m x) \right] \quad (4)$$

$$A_m = \left\{ \frac{2}{\lambda_m [J_0^2(\lambda_m) + J_1^2(\lambda_m)]} \right\} \times \left\{ x_{\text{int},o} J_1(\lambda_m x_{\text{int},o}) + \xi_{O_{2,o,p}} [J_1(\lambda_m) - x_{\text{int},o} J_1(\lambda_m x_{\text{int},o})] \right\} \quad (4a)$$

where

$$Y_{O_2} = \frac{C_{O_2}}{C_{O_2,0}}, \quad Z = \frac{z}{R_t}, \quad x = \frac{r}{R_t}, \quad x_{int,o} = \frac{R_{int,o}}{R_t},$$

$$\zeta = \frac{R_t (v_z)}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2,m}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \xi_{0_2,o,p} = \frac{C_{0_2,o,p}}{C_{O_2,0}}$$

Note that $\xi_{0_2,o,p} = 0$ when the annular stream acts as the carbon surface protective boundary layer, and $\xi_{0_2,o,p} = 1$ when the annular stream provides no protection to the carbon surface from oxygen attack.

λ_m 's are obtained by solving the following equation for its roots.

$$\lambda J_1(\lambda) - \alpha J_0(\lambda) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where

$$\alpha = \frac{kR_t}{\mathcal{D}_{O_2,m}} \quad (5a)$$

Using Eq (4), the following analytical results were obtained:

Local oxygen diffusive flux at the tube surface at any Z,

$$\left(\dot{N}_{O_2}, \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}} \right) = \left(\frac{2\mathcal{D}_{O_2,m}C_{O_2,0}}{R_t} \right) \left[\sum_{m=1}^{m=\infty} A_m \lambda_m J_1(\lambda_m) e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_m^2}{\zeta} \right) Z} \right] \quad (6a)$$

Local carbon loss rate at the tube surface at any Z,

$$\left(\dot{N}_C, \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}} \right) = \left(\frac{2\mathcal{D}_{O_2,m}C_{O_2,0}}{R_t} \right) \left[\sum_{m=1}^{m=\infty} A_m \lambda_m J_1(\lambda_m) e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_m^2}{\zeta} \right) Z} \right] \quad (6b)$$

Surface area averaged carbon loss rate at the tube surface,

$$\left(\dot{N}_{C,av}, \frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^2 \text{ s}} \right) = \left(\frac{2\mathcal{D}_{O_2,m}C_{O_2,0}\zeta}{L} \right) \sum_{m=1}^{m=\infty} \left[\frac{A_m J_1(\lambda_m)}{\lambda_m} \left(1 - e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_m^2}{\zeta} \right) \left(\frac{L}{R_t} \right)} \right) \right] \quad (6c)$$

where L is the carbon tube length.

Oxygen molecular diffusivity in a gas mixture at any pressure and temperature conditions is calculated using the information given in [7, 11]. The carbon tube average interior surface recession rate is given by

$$\frac{dR_t}{dt} = \frac{M_c \dot{N}_{c,av}}{\rho_{c-c}} \quad (7)$$

where M_c is the molecular weight of carbon (=12gm per mol), and ρ_{c-c} is the density of the carbon-carbon composite material.

The bulk oxygen concentration at any Z is given by

$$Y_{0_2,b} = 2 \left[\sum_{m=1}^{m=\infty} \frac{A_m J_1(\lambda_m)}{\lambda_m} e^{-\left(\frac{\lambda_m^2}{\zeta}\right)Z} \right] \quad (8)$$

where $Y_{0_2,b} = \frac{C_{0_2,b}}{C_{0_2,o}}$ and $C_{0_2,b}$ is the bulk oxygen concentration in the units of $\left(\frac{\text{mol}}{\text{cm}^3}\right)$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figures 2-5 show the computed results for the typical parametric values of pressure $p = 101.3 \text{ kPa}$, $\langle v_z \rangle = 100 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, $T = 2000\text{K}$ and the initial oxygen mole fraction of 0.005. The geometrical dimensions of the test section shown in Fig. 1 used to compute these results are $L = 5.0 \text{ cm}$, $R_t = 0.4762 \text{ cm}$, and $R_{\text{int},o} = 0.2778 \text{ cm}$. Figure 2 shows the dimensionless oxygen concentration profiles in the field of gas flowing through the carbon-carbon tube for the case of no oxidation protection provided by the annular boundary layer flow to the tube surface. A decrease in the dimensionless oxygen concentration, Y_{0_2} , is observed in Fig. 2a with an increase in the dimensionless radial distance, x , from the center line to the tube surface ($x = 1.0$) at any Z plane. Figure 2b shows a decrease in Y_{0_2} with an increase in Z at any x -plane. Figure 3 shows the oxygen profiles as a function of radial and axial positions for the case of oxidation protection provided by the annular boundary layer flow to the tube interior surface. Oxygen concentration profiles shown in Fig. 3 are similar to that shown in Fig. 2. On comparison of Fig. 3a profiles with Fig. 2a profiles, we find lower oxygen concentration at the tube surface for the protective relative to the non-protective case (as expected). Figure 4 compares the bulk oxygen concentration profiles for the non-protected ($\xi_{0_2,o,p} = 1.0$) and protected ($\xi_{0_2,o,p} = 0.0$) boundary layer flows. These profiles appear to have about the same slope. Figure 5 compares the dimensionless local oxygen flux profiles for the non-protected ($\xi_{0_2,o,p} = 1.0$) and protected ($\xi_{0_2,o,p} = 0.0$) boundary layer flows. It is apparent that the dimensionless local oxygen flux for the non-protected case is larger than that for the protected case at an axial position.

The degree of protection afforded by an inert gas boundary layer as predicted by the computational model is given in Table 1 for both 1500K and 2000K. It is apparent that the carbon mass loss is reduced by a factor of about 3.3 by the nitrogen gas protective boundary layer flow at 1500K. The mass loss reduction factor is 3.0 at 2000K. We therefore conclude that an inert/equilibrium synthetic gas boundary layer flow can provide protection to a carbon-carbon composite surface from oxidation at an elevated gas temperature environment. The predicted protection under other flow conditions, temperature and pressures is under investigation.

Figure 2. Computed oxygen profiles as a function of a) radial position and b) axial position at $T=2000K$ and $p = 101.3$ kPa where the initial oxygen mole fraction at $Z = 0$ is 0.005 both in the centerline and boundary layer flow.

Figure 3. Computed oxygen profiles as a function of a) radial position and b) axial position at $T = 2000K$ and $p = 101.3$ kPa where the initial oxygen mole fraction at $Z = 0$ is 0.005 in the centerline flow and is 0.000 in the boundary layer flow.

Figure 4. Comparison of computed dimensionless bulk oxygen concentration profiles for non-protected and protected boundary layer flows at $T = 2000\text{K}$ and $p = 101.3\text{ kPa}$.

Figure 5. Comparison of computed dimensionless local oxygen fluxes for non-protected and protected boundary layer flows at $T = 2000\text{K}$ and $p = 101.3\text{ kPa}$.

TABLE 1
 Effect of the Inert Gas Protective Boundary Layer on the Carbon Mass Loss
 p (pressure) = 101.33 kPa $\langle v_z \rangle = 100 \frac{\text{cm}}{\text{s}}$ $y_{\text{O}_2,0} = 0.005$

$\xi_{\text{O}_2,0,p} = 1$ (no protection provided by the boundary layer)				$\xi_{\text{O}_2,0,p} = 0$ (protection provided by the boundary layer)			
Tube surface area averaged carbon mass loss rate. $(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}})$		Tube interior surface recession rate $(\frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{h}})$		Tube surface area averaged carbon mass loss rate. $(\frac{\mu\text{g}}{\text{cm}^2 \cdot \text{s}})$		Tube interior surface recession rate $(\frac{\mu\text{m}}{\text{h}})$	
T=1500K	T=2000K	T=1500K	T=2000K	T=1500K	T=2000K	T=1500K	T=2000K
0.386	3.18	7.97	66.0	0.116	1.06	2.40	22.0

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6. BIOGRAPHIES

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